

The Effectiveness of Using Short Story to Improve Students' Ability in Reading English Texts: Experimental Study at the Eight Grade Students of MTs. AL-Madani Pelulan in Academic

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Abstract: This research is aimed at finding out the improving students' ability in reading texts by using short story at the eight grade students of MTs. AL-Madani Pelulan The kind of the research is an experimental research. The population of this research is 54 students of the eight grade students of MTs. AL-Madani Pelulan in which all of it as sample and divided into two groups that are XA as experimental group and XB as control group. The experimental group is taught by using short story as instrument and the control group is taught without short story or based on real object. The techniques of collecting data use multiple choice. The data collected were analyzed statistically by using t-test formula. The result of statistical analysis of t-test it was 3,13 which was higher than the critical value of t-table, it was 2,006 (0.05) and 1,675 (0.01). It means that t-test is higher than t-table in 0.05% of significance level and 52 of degree of freedom. Thus, it can concluded that the use of short story as media to improve students' ability in reading text is enough interesting to apply in teaching reading texts. It means the alternative hypothesis (H_a) was accepted and the null hypothesis (H_o) was rejected.

Key Words: Short Story, Reading English Texts.

A. Introduction

English as an International language is often considered as the language of the world. It is used by most people, as communication in international congress, gathering, making explanation, analyzing situation or discussion the relative merits of one procedure. English is also as medium to transfer the science and technology.

In Indonesia, English is also learned as the most important foreign language. This language has been introduced to the student from the secondary school level as compulsory subject. English teachers are obligated to teach four major skills: reading, listening, speaking, and writing integrative. One of primary goal in teaching English is to enable the students to communicate by

using English as the target language.¹

As International language, and the first foreign language in this country, it is very important to be acquired by all people in this country. One of the keys for acquiring this language is through reading. Because, by this way, we would be easier to acquire four major skills in the English, in other hand we would be able to find a lot of new information to expand our knowledge, and to make our speaking or pronunciation would be better as well.

But in fact, we had found a lot of people lazy to read, especially our students with several reasons. This case be able to make their ability in reading will not improve. Therefore, we must have solution to make our students interested in reading, and provide them interesting reading material.

One of example for interesting reading materials is short story. Short story may interest the students or readers, because its contents consist of simple and easy understanding. Starting from the statement above, the writer decides to investigate the effectiveness of using short story to improve students’ ability in reading English texts: Experimental study at the eight grade students of MTs. AL-Madani Pelulan.

B. Review Of Related Literatures

1. Concept of Reading

Teachers should stimulate students to read. This can be done by giving lead in questions that will help students focus on the reading topic.² Generally, reading is process done by the reader to get the message expressed by the writer through the writer language. However, it is not simple process as it is.

Reading is very complex process in which the recognition and achievement of written symbols are influenced by the perceptual skill, the experience, the language background, the mind set, and reasoning ability of the readers as we anticipates meaning of the basis of what we are read”³. Meanwhile, Pappas, define reading as thinking. It is not just recognition of words, but involves gaining meaning from the frontal symbols (word) an the understanding meaning of carries. Furthermore, he explains that reading is predominantly visual thinking skill, utilizing the eyes and the higher mental process. It is the methods that form reaction in the mind.⁴

Another scholar, Burns⁵ wrote that reading is thinking process, in the

¹ Widdowso, H.G, *Teaching Language As Communication*, (New York: Oxford University Press. 1990), 132.

²Burns, Paul, Et Al, *Teaching Reading Into Day’s Elementary School*, (New Jersey: Houghton Mifflin Comp. Inc. 1984), 509.

³ Haris, Chester W. . *Encyclopedia Of Education Research*, (New York: NhteMcMillan. 1969), 7.

⁴Pappas, George, Oson David, . *Perspectives’ Children LanguageandLanguage Teaching Arts*, February 227-229 1970), 11.

⁵ Burns, Paul, Et Al, Op. Cit, 10.

extent, the readers must be able to use the information to make inferences and read critically and reactively to understand the figurative language, determine the authors purpose, evaluate the idea presented and apply the reading to actual situation.

To support the opinion above, Burn quoted the opinion of Chambers and Lorry as follows: "Reading is more that recognizing the word for which certain combination of letters about a correct recall. Means, experimenting with choice rote, and devising some mean of evaluating the result".⁶ Reading an foreign language as "the grasping of the full linguistics meaning of what is read in subject with in the common experience of the culture of which the language is centralpart". Another definitions is that "reading is process of understanding language pattern from its written". Reading can be classed into two categories, intensive and extensive reading. Reading activity which is related to further progress in language learning under the teacher guidance. In this type of reading, teacher control the reading topic, material and activities, it will provides a basis for education of the faculties of structure, and fo the extension of vocabulary.⁷ Meanwhile, extensive reading develops the students own face according to their individual ability. in this case, the activityis not completely controlled by teacher. Students are learned to read without the teacher role. The extensive reading activity is mostly concerned with the purpose of training students to read directly and fluently, for his or her own work without the assistance of the teachers.

2. Types of Reading

There are many types of reading such as: skimming, scanning, idea reading, exploratory reading, study reading, and critical reading.

1. Skimming

Skimming is used to denote the method of glancing through text in order to become familiar with the gist of the content. Skimming is kind of reading which make our eyes moving more rapid. In this case, to find, recognizing or exploring the information or illumination from the text. Skimming means looking quickly to get only mean idea. Furthermore the method of skimming can be (1) preview, (2) overview and (3) survey.⁸ When we try to find information in a text quikly, we are skimming the text. To skim a text means to read quikly and find out what the text is about. For example, the students have the habit to skimming the newspaper in the morning. Because they should harry up to the school, and they do not have times to read it through. Thus, the students skim it. They are looking at the headlines title, of important new item, key sentences printed in big letters.⁹

⁶ Burns, Paul, Et Al, Op. Cit, 114.

⁷ Rivers, *Teaching Foreign Language Skill*. (Chicago University Press. 1968) p. 229

⁸ Wiryacitra, . *Ascientific Reading Program Teaching English Forum*, (3 Volume. 1982), 28.

⁹ Wiryacitra, . *ibid*, 28.

When we skim a reading material, we look at important piece of news very quickly to get the general ideas of what the text is about. Here are some characteristics of skimming, when we skim, we: (1) look at the key items like titles, statement in the big letters, eat (2) do not look at individual word, (3) are interested in the main ideas of the news; we usually read the first sentences of paragraph, (4) do not the dictionary to check the meaning of word.

2. Scanning

Scanning is looking for information or for the answer to a certain question or question. Sometime it is done before reading in detail to see whether the reading has the information one is looking for; if it does not, the readers may decide not to read in detailed. Sometimes scanning is done after reading in detail in order to review a particular point or piece of information.

Scanning is almost the opposite of skimming, in skimming we are looking for the general idea of text. In scannin we are looking for the specific details. Although scanning is almost the opposite skimming, therefore, it is true that scanning usually follows skimming.

3. Idea Reading

This reading for mean ideas is tehnique of rapidly reading in which the eyes move rapidly. They catch large phases at each glance and register with the brain only the most significant words or ideas in those phrases. Successful ideas reading is perhaps one of the most efficient.

4. Exploratory Reading

Exploratory reading involves more detail than the techniques mentioned before. The emphasis of this technique is recognizing and understanding main ideas more thoroughly. The readers will be related to others idea in previous knowledge of the subject.¹⁰

5. Study reading

Study reading is a type in which we must get maximal understanding of the main ideas and their relationship. This is the type that we must apply to our text books. We may apply it our contracts, legal paper, technical manual, instruction and other similar materials. Here we can frequently deal with materials that we must read and understand and remember for future use.

6. Critical reading

To apply technique of critical reading. We should go back and consider carefully what we know about the source of the reading material. What are the possible bases or ulterior motive that is publisher or other’s background experience and potential knowledge of thesubject? We should look at the reading material for inconsistence, logic or false analogies. Another important thing is an awareness of emotionally loaded words that appeal to basic emotions . By experience, we may learn to spot some of these types of appeals through quick scanning for the clues the author provides.

¹⁰ Burns, Paul, Et Al, 97.

Reading is probably the most importance skill we need to succeeded in our study. We have to read lengthy degress of detailed and the difficulty. If we read accurately, we will fail to understand some of information and ideas that we read. If we read slowly we will spent times to read assignment. That is why in order to read accurately and efficiently, we have know skill and reading technique.

Finally in order to read efficiently, a technique of reading any article or books, it's called SQ3R. These letters stand for the five steps, namely; survey, question, reading, recall, and review.¹¹

a. Survey

To know where we are going to, and also how the author has organized his materials. Furthermore, before we are start to read the chapter of the text, we look at the final couple of paragraph which may include the summary and which will very likely repeat the major ideas of the chapter. If the materials are completely new for us, we probably spent a little time to read the first couple sentences of each new topic, so we can gain an overall picture of the context.

b. Question

The survey step has given us general overview of the material, helping to focus to the main idea and supporting detailed in each of the section and to the information which has already know. Moreover, the modern text books has question in the end of each chapter, so that if we read the chapter, we will know what to concerate on.

c. Reading

As we read, we can concentrate on answering the question that we have mind. Notice what the author thinks is importance, and how active all the times. We use the knowledge if we are already have about the subject to relate that we are read.

d. Recall

In this step, we try to notice of what we read. Most of the readers found that notes telling a great help in getting information fixed in their mind. If we can make an outline of each chapter wich we have read, it make us really know what we read and we have useful summary. Moreover we want to read back its reading passage.

e. Review

This step reminds us to think over what is mentioned in the readingpassage e. It mean that we have to review the passage, as linguists say: The more frequently we review, no read passage, the larger information that we will get from the materials.

3. Factor Influences Reading Skill

Some factors which may raise problem in understanding the reading

¹¹Lin Lougheed, 1976. *Educational Measurement third Edition*. (New York: American communal on, Educational. Acemillan, 1976), 23.

materials, the total program of reading instruction, the child own personality, interest, motivation and his out of school,¹²

On this particular matter, there are also some other factor influencing reading skill which will be presented below:¹³

1. Intelligenc

Intelligence is general capacity to learn, the numbers of ideas that the students understand and the depth of his understanding, the rail at which he associates what he read with her previous knowledge or experience will be largely dependent to her intelligence.

2. Experience

Experience is the dept and broad experience of student's difference from those of the other students. A student with a limited experience many of may have difficulties in comprehending many of the ideas and activities while others are quite familiar.

3. Mechanics of reading

Mechanics of reading is the skill of recondition the ability to handbooks properly and to read left to right on line of print determines the flow of reading. If students does not have those skill or can not the smoothly comprehending, they will be difficult to obtain specific information from the passage.

4. Interest

Interest is deep of comprehending which students gain will be indirect proportion to the amount of the interest they already have in the selection.

5. Skill of comprehension

Skill of comprehension is ability to comprehend what one read to develop gradually from the sample to the complex skill. It is the teacher task to prove the students with the skill of developing good attitudes toward reading and the skills of thoughtful, purposeful reading.

4. Measurement of Reading

A teacher is interest not only in measurin the success of his pupils in mastering a specific skill but also the effectiveness of his course reading, especially for the higher level of readers. This is because partiular method is applied to measure the students reading speed or time reading.¹⁴

Finally there are four major categories of rough division of types of reading question that is direct references, influences supposition, and evaluating¹⁵,

a. Direct references

Direct references are essentially making use of the text simple as exemplification of the language system. It can be answered without the readers, need to recognize how the system is being use. Question of this kind can

¹² Zinzit Magart, *The Reading Proses, The Teacher And The Learner*, (U.S.A. 1989.), 22.

¹³ Rivers, and Tarigan, 95.

¹⁴ Lin Loughed. *Op. Cit.* p, 126.

¹⁵ Burns, Paul, *Et Al*, *Op. Cit.*, 147.

be often answered without references to text at all and there may not be need to refer to the line, which the word appears.

b. Inference

Inference is directed toward the discover of the relationship between the sentence and manner which they combine in communication. In concerned with the smaller unit also, but whereas the direct references question realities item in text to their types in the system to the language. Inference question relates in the text with other item in the text.

c. Supposition short story

The requires the readers to say what they are suppose to say based on certain language items. It is not always easy to distinguish between question of this type and inference question. Perhaps they are directed at getting the readers to related the text to the wider situation of communication for intance. "why does the writer say that was necessary for the apes to the descend from trees"?

d. Evaluation

Evaluation is suitable for learners who already acquired a high degree of sophistication in the language. It typically the readers to assess the value of reading passage and the effectiveness of the way information has been organized and expressed question of this kind can properly formulated.

5. Ability Concept

Ability is the quality or power of be able to do something, physical, Mental financial or legal power of perform.¹⁶ "ability as essential capacity or power to do something physical or mental". Based on those statements, the writer concludes that ability is quality or powered each child with change the attitude, behavior and skill.¹⁷

1. Factors influencing ability

There are two major factors which may promote the children ability, there are internal and external factors.

a. Internal factors

Internal factors consist of: (a) Children wishes for what they want to ability. (b) Personal interest, which influence, the areas of the children aspiration. (c) Past experience with successes strengthening aspirations and failure weakening them. (d) The personality pattern which influences both of the kind and strength of children aspiration. (e) Sex, with boys aspiring higher than the girls. (f) Socioeconomic status, with those of the middle upper groups aspiring higher that those lower group. (g) Racial background with those of minority group status often aspiring unrealities high as a compensation,¹⁸

¹⁶Finnochioro, Mary, English As Second Language From Theory ToPractice. New Edition New York. Regen Publishing Company.Inc. 1983), 32.

¹⁷Hornby, As. 1995. *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary Fifth Edition*, Oxford University Press.

¹⁸Hurlock, R and Louis, .The Future of Education Perceptive on tommooro,Schooling, Research for Better

b. External factors

The external factor consist of, (a) Parental ambitions, which are higher for first born later than children, (b) Social expectation which emphasize that those who are successful in all areas if they wish, (c) Pressures to set aspiration in areas importance to the group, (d) Group emphasize on sex appropriateness of aspiration, (e) Cultural traditions or tribes which hold that all people can achieve anything they wish if they try hard enough, (f) Social values which vary with areas of achievement, (g) mass media which encourage achievement aspiration, (h) Social rewards of high achievement and social neglect or rejection for lower achievements, (i) Competition with siblings and peers in the hope of the showing ones superiority over them.

2. Effect of ability

The self-concept is greatly influences by whether students regard themselves success, or failures. According to other people, they may be successful but in the fact they fail. This also means that who is objectively successful can be subjectively as fail.¹⁹

C. Research Method

1. Research Design

An experimental design is one of the priciest methods to examine a cause and effect²⁰. So, the method that will be used in this research is experimental method, and the sample in this reasearch that will be divided in two groups “Experimental treatment and possibly a control group”. Namely:

- a. Control Group
- b. Experimental Group

The design of two groups are follows;

Table 1. The Experimental Design

Group	Pre – test	Independent variable	Post- test
E	X1	X	X2
C	Y1	-	Y2

Where :

- E ; Experimental group
C ; Control group
X1 ; Pre- test
X ; Treatment toward experimental group with Short Story

School. London: Philadelphia Pencyvania. 1975), 342.

¹⁹ Wiryacitra, Op. Cit, 2.

²⁰ Ibnu, S., *Dasar- Dasar Metodologi Penelitian.* (Malang: Universitas Negeri Malang, 2003), 150.

Y2 : Post – test.

Both of the groups have equal time, equal test, equal right and different treatment which will be conducted into three steps namely pre-test, treatment and post test.

Meanwhile, for the seek of the data collection, testing method will completely be applied instead of other supporting resources. Then the data will be obtained later wisely analyzed by applying basic statistical computation.

2. Population and Sample

1. Population

Population is all research objects or subjects wheather consist of concrete or abstract things, event, or a phenomenon whose the same characteristic as the data resources,²¹

The population of this research is the eight grade students of MTs. AL-Madani Pelulan, which consist of two classes, and each class consist of 27 students. So, the total number of the students from the two classes are 54 students.

2. Sampel

Sampel is small number of people which chosen from a larger group. ²² if the population is more than 100, it would be better to take between 10% - 15%, 20% - 25%, as the sample. But, if the population is less than 100, it would be better to take all of them as the sample.

So, the writer decided to take of all the population as the sample based on Arikunto opinion above. The total sample has been taken by the writer are two classes, such as: Class VIIIA with 27 students will be experimental group, and Class VIIIB with 27 students will be control group.

3. Research Instrument

The data in this research will be collected by using test. Test is a series of question or exercises use to measure the skill, knowledge, intelligence, ability or talent who possessed by individual or group²³.

The test will be used in this study is Multiple choice. “Multiple choice is a test of which have a precisely answer”²⁴.

For the test consists of 20 questions of multiple choice and the test will be scored 10 for each items answered correctly in multiple choice test. The highest possible score will be 100, and the lowest possible score will be 0. Individual scores of group will be analyzed statically as the consideration in drawing conclusion of the research. The following measurement of the students’ achievement.²⁵

²¹ Arikunto, Suharsimi. *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Edisi revisi. (Jakarta: PT.Fineta Cipta. 2010), 38.

²²Hornby, As. . *Oxford Advanced Learner’s Dictionary Fifth Edition*, (Oxford University Press,1995), 104.

²³ Arikunto, Suharsimi.. *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Edisi revisi. Jakarta:PT. Rineka Cipta. 2010), 30.

²⁴ Sudjana, Nana.. *Penilaian Hasil Proses Belajar Mengajar*.(Bandung; Rosda Karya, 2010) p. 36

²⁵ Arikunto, Suharsimi. Log Cit. p, 120.

Table 2. The Measurements of the Students’ Achievement

Degree	Qualification
80-100	Excellent
70-79	Good
60-69	Fair
50-59	Poor
0-49	Very Poor

The table above means that:

If the score is 0 to 49 is classified “Very Poor”

If the score is 50 to 59 is classified “Poor”

If the score is 60 to 69 is classified “fair”

If the score is 70 to 79 is classified “Good”

If the score is 80 to 100 is classified “Excellent”

This test is aimed to know the students’ ability in reading.

4. Data Collection Procedures

A test is a list of the question or exercise that personal have. In this research the writer will use test and sequences of procedure which can be divided into three mayor catagories.²⁶

a. Pre-test

The first meeting the researcher will give the students test both of experimental group and control group which is aimed to know students’ reading ability before treatment will be given for experimental group. The result of the test will be counted for the data compared with the result of the post-test.

b. Treatment

The treatment will be given in two meeting regularly, where the exspermental group will be taught by using disscusion the kind of the text, how to identify the main idea of short story.

c. Post-test

Post test will be given after the material explained. After teaching process or treatment, the reseacher will give test to both of two groups which will be tested for second time. It is aimed to know the improvement of student ability in reading.

5. Data Analysis Procedure

To analyze the result of the test, the following test will be wisely applied:

- a. Identifying the sample’s scores of the experimental group of their pre-test (X_1) and post-test (X_2) scores, and control group of their pre-test (Y_1) and post-test (Y_2)
- b. Inserting the student’s scores into the data tables.
- c. Identifying the students individual deviation (D) of sample score (post-test result) to pre-test scores. The following formula is completely applied.

²⁶ Arikunto, Suharsimi. Ibid, 114.

1. Deviation of the experimental group

$$Dx = X_2 - X_1$$

Where:

Dx = Deviation of the experimental group

X_1 = Score from pre-test

X_2 = Score from post-test

2. Deviation of the control group

$$Dy = Y_2 - Y_1$$

Where:

Dy = Deviation of the control group

Y_1 = Score from pre-test of the control group

Y_2 = Score from post-test of the control group

- d. Identifying the mean deviation of each group (D) by applying these formulas:

1. Identifying the deviation of the experimental group

$$\overline{Dx} = \frac{\sum Dx}{Nx}$$

Where:

\overline{Dx} = Mean deviation of the control group

Dx = Deviation of the experimental group

Nx = Total samples of the experimental group

2. Identifying the deviation of the control group

$$\overline{Dy} = \frac{\sum Dy}{Ny}$$

Where:

\overline{Dy} = Mean deviation of the control group

Dy = Deviation of the control group

Ny = Total samples of the control group

- e. Identifying the mean deviation where it is significant or not

$$t = \frac{\overline{Dx} - \overline{Dy}}{\sqrt{\left\{ \frac{\sum D^2x + \sum D^2y}{Nx + Ny - 2} \right\} \left\{ \frac{1}{Nx} + \frac{1}{Ny} \right\}}}$$

Where:

t = the significance of the experimental group to control group

\overline{Dx} = Mean deviation of the experimental group

\overline{Dy} = Mean deviation of the control group

$\sum D^2x$ = The square deviation of the experimental group

$\sum D^2y$ = The square deviation of the control group

N_x = The total samples of the experimental group

N_y = The total samples of the control group.²⁷

f. Consult the result between the results of t-test to t-table.

If the results or t-test > t-table, the null hypothesis is rejected. If the results or t-test < t-table than the null hypothesis is not rejected.

D. Research Finding And Discussion

1. Research Finding

This chapter containing the statistical analysis of the data obtained during conducting the research. The description of data leads to the elaboration of the all finding in this investigation, how to interpret the data, and concludes the result of the study.

By presenting the results of the study in this research, the writer would like to present the description of the data obtained. The population of this study was the eight grade students of MTs. AL-Madani Pelulan. And the sample in this study divided into two classes: They are XIII A as the experimental class and XIII B as the control class, the total number of the sample is 54 students.

In doing this researcch, the writer gave pre-test for both of groups, they are tested by some test. After that, the writer gave treatment for Experimental group, and the treatment was given three times during the expriment. Finally the writer gave post test for experimental and control groups. The content of post test is same with previous test. The test consists of 20 questions of multiple choice and the test was scored 10 for each items answered correctly in multiple choice test. The highest possible score was 100, and the lowest possible score was 0.

The students’ individual score for both experimental and control groups can be seen on the following tables. They described briefly based on students’ achievement in pre-test and post-test.

Table 1.1. Deviation of pre-test and post-test of the experimental group.

Subject	Pre-Test (X1)	Pos-test (X2)	Deviation (DX)	D ² X
1	75	80	5	25
2	70	80	10	100
3	75	75	0	0
4	80	90	10	100
5	70	70	0	0
6	75	85	10	100
7	60	70	10	100
8	80	90	10	100
9	60	75	15	225
10	75	85	10	100
11	70	80	10	100

²⁷ Arikunto, Suharsimi. Ibid, 152.

12	65	70	5	25
13	60	70	10	100
14	80	90	10	100
15	80	90	10	100
16	75	80	5	25
17	75	80	5	25
18	75	85	10	100
19	50	50	0	0
20	80	85	5	25
25	80	85	5	25
22	60	65	5	25
23	85	100	15	225
24	80	90	10	100
25	70	80	10	100
26	70	85	15	225
27	75	80	5	25
Total	1950	2165	215	2175

From the table above, we can see that students' total score in pre-test of experimental group is 1950 and the total score in post- test 2165, and deviation score of experimental students is 215. The deviation score of experimental students is obtained from the result of the post –test is subtracted the result of the pre-test score and D^2X is gotten from D^2 cross X of the Experimental group. The square deviation score of the Experimental group (D^2X) is 2175.

Table 1.2. Deviation Score of Pre-test and Pos-test of control group.

Subject	Pre-test (Y1)	Post-test (Y2)	Deviation (DY)	D^2y
1	70	75	5	25
2	70	70	0	0
3	65	70	5	25
4	60	60	0	0
5	75	80	5	25
6	70	65	-5	25
7	60	65	5	25
8	80	90	10	100
9	70	75	5	25
10	75	75	0	0
11	65	65	0	0
12	65	70	5	25
13	60	60	0	0
14	60	60	0	0

15	75	75	0	0
16	70	65	-5	25
17	70	75	5	25
18	75	75	0	0
19	65	70	5	25
20	65	70	5	25
21	65	65	0	0
22	70	70	0	0
23	60	60	0	0
24	80	90	10	100
25	80	85	5	25
26	75	75	0	0
27	75	75	0	0
Total	1870	1930	55	500

From the table above, we can see that the student total score in pre-test of the control group is 1870 and the total score in post test is 1930. Then, total score for deviation of the control group (DY) is 55, the deviation of individual score of the control group is obtained from the result of post- test score is subtracted by pre- test score. D^2Y is gotten from D^2 Cross y. D^2Y Score is 500.

2. Data Analysis

- a. Calculating the student’s mean deviations score of two variable X and Y. The following the formula was applied:

- 1). Calculating the student’s mean deviation scores of experimental groups

(X). the formula was applied :

$$\bar{Dx} = \frac{\sum Dx}{Nx}$$

Where:

Dx = Mean deviation

$\sum Dx$ = The total deviation of experimental group (215)

Nx = Total sample of experimental group (27)

So, the mean deviation score of experimental group (X) was:

$$\bar{Dx} = \frac{215}{27}$$

$$\bar{Dx} = 7,96$$

- 2). Calculating the student's mean deviation scores of control group (Y). the formula was applied :

$$\bar{Dy} = \frac{\sum Dy}{Ny}$$

Where:

Dy = Mean deviation

$\sum Dy$ = The total deviation of control group (55)

Ny = Total sample of control group (27)

So, the mean deviation score of control group (Y) was:

$$\bar{Dy} = \frac{55}{27}$$

$$\bar{Dy} = 2,03$$

- b.** Identifying the significance of the mean deviation scores from two mean deviation scores. the following formula was applied to countering the significance or not:

$$t = \frac{\bar{Dx} - \bar{Dy}}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{\sum D^2 X + \sum D^2 y}{Nx + Ny - 2}\right) \left(\frac{1}{Nx} + \frac{1}{Ny}\right)}}$$

Where:

t = t-test

\bar{Dx} = 7,96

\bar{Dy} = 2,03

$\sum D^2 x$ = 2175

$\sum D^2 y$ = 500

Nx = 27

Ny = 27

The computation based on formula was:

$$t = \frac{7,96 - 2,03}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{2175 + 500}{27 + 27 - 2}\right) \left(\frac{1}{27} + \frac{1}{27}\right)}}$$

$$t = \frac{5,93}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{2675}{52}\right)\left(\frac{2}{27}\right)}}$$

$$t = \frac{5,93}{\sqrt{(51,44)(0,07)}}$$

$$t = \frac{5,93}{\sqrt{(3,60)}}$$

$$t = \frac{5,93}{1,89}$$

$$t = 3,13$$

3. Discussion

In this part of chapter discussed all the result of data analysis and compared those results with the value of *t-table* that is aimed to test the hypothesis whether Alternative hypothesis (HA) is accepted so that the Null hypothesis (H0) is completely rejected or vice versa, the Null hypothesis (N0) is accepted so that Alternative hypothesis (HA) is rejected . However, there are some essential factors need to define before comparing those results. Those factors are the degree of freedom and the level of significance used in comparing the result of *t-test* toward *t-table*.

1. The degree of freedom (df)

There is a common way to think of degrees of freedom is as the number of independent pieces of information available to estimate another piece of information. More concretely, the number of degrees of freedom is the number of independent observations in a sample of data that are available to estimate a parameter of the population from which that sample is drawn.

The following formula is used to define the degree of freedom in this study:

$$df = Nx + Ny - 2$$

Where : *df* = Degree of freedom

Nx = The total sample of experimental group

Ny = The total sample of control group

The election of the formula above as the formula to define the degree of freedom is not without considering any reason. But, it was because of the comparison between the result of *t-test* and the value of *t-table* is held by using one tailed test.

By using the following formula the degree of freedom can be defined:

$$df = Nx + Ny - 2$$

$$df = 27 + 27 - 2$$

$$df = 52$$

2. Determining level of significance

Determining the level of significance considered crucial to define in which

level the comparison between the result of *t-test* and *t-table* should be taken. Here the researcher used the level of significance at 5% = 0.05 level with degree of freedom 52

The steps in comparing the result of *t-test* to the value of *t-table* can be described through the following illustration:

- a. If the result of *t-test* is equals or higher than the value of *t-table* at confidence level 5% ($t\text{-test} \geq t\text{-table}$). This indicates that the degree of difference between the means of deviation score is significant at confidence level 5% (0.05)
- b. If the result of *t-test* is lower than the value of *t-table* at confidence level 5% ($t\text{-test} < t\text{-table}$). This indicates that the degree of difference between the means deviation score is not significant at confidence level 5% (0.05)

The computation of correlation between two means of deviation score above is computed by using *t-test*. It found that the result of computation is 3,13, and then this figure is consulted to the value of *t-table* where the researcher determined the level of significance is 5%, and the degree of freedom is 52.

According to the *t-table* enclosed in this study, the closest degree of freedom for 52 is at d.f 54 with level of significance 5% (0.05) for one tailed test. The result of *t-test* can be compared with the value of *t-table* as follow:

$$t\text{-test} = 3,13 > t\text{-table} = 2,006 \text{ at level of significance } 5\% (0.05)$$

From the result of comparison between the result of *t-test* with the value of *t-table* above, can be seen that the result of *t-test* is higher than the value of *t-table*. So, it can be interpreted that the Alternative hypothesis (H_A) is accepted and Null hypothesis (H₀) is completely rejected at level of significance 5% (0.05).

Based on the result of data obtained above, the statement of problem that stated “is short story effective to improve students’ ability in reading English texts at the eight grade students of MTs. AL-Madani Pelulan’. is completely answered. It was proved by the differences in students’ achievement where the mean of deviation score of experimental group is higher than the mean of deviation score obtained by control group. So, the short story effective to improve students’ ability in reading English texts at the eight grade students of MTs. AL-Madani Pelulan.

E. Conclusion And Suggestion

1. Conclusion

Through this particular investigation, in general it can be concluded that the using of short story has positive effect in helping the students to improve their ability in reading texts. This conclusion is taken as a result of treatment of the mean of pre-test score with a finishing of a t-test formula it is obtained that the critical score of a t-table. This critical scores is higher than indication of t-table levels of 0.05 (99.95 %) equal to 2.006 and at confidence level of 0.01 (99.99%), with 1.675 the degrees of freedom 52 on the one tailed test indication.

This mean that the Alternative Hypothesis (H_a) is accepted, which read that,”Using short story effective to improve students’ ability in reading English texts

at the eight grade students of MTs. AL-Madani Pelulan. And the Null Hypothesis (Ho) is rejected, which read that," using short story doesn't effective to improve the students' ability in reading English texts at the eight grade students of MTs. AL Madani Pelulan.

2. Suggestion

Based on the above conclusion, the researcher offer some suggestion to be considered by English teachers and Students.

1. For English teachers

- a. English teachers should be creative in teaching and creat an enjoyable situation during the teaching learning process especially in reading texts, so that the students will be interested in learning English.
- b. English teachers should use English in the class; it can helps students to improve their english.

2. For the students

- a. The students' should improve their knowledge and also study hard, especially in improving their knowladge by using short story in reading.
- b. The students should practice their English everyday, thus it can helps them improving their English.

References

- Arikunto, Suharsimi. 2010. *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Edisi revisi. Jakarta: PT.Rineta Cipta.
- Burns, Paul, Et Al,1984. *Teaching Reading Into Day's Elementary School*, New Jersey: Houghton Mifflin Comp. Inc.
- Finnochioro, Mary, 1983. *English As Second Language From Theory To Practice*. New Edition New York.Regan Publishing Company.Inc.
- Haris, Chester W. 1969. *Encyclopedia Of Education Research*; New York: NhteMcMillan.
- Hornby, As. 1995. *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary Fifth Edition*, Oxford University Press.
- Hurlock, R and Louis, 1975.*The Future of Education Perceptive on tommoro Schooling, Research for Better Scho* London:Philadelphia Pencyvania.
- Ibnu, S. 2003. *Dasar- Dasar Metodologi Penelitian*. Malang: Universitas Negeri Malang.
- Kincaid, Jamaica. "Girl". 1994 *The Vintage Book of Contemporary American Short Stories*. Ed. Tobias Wolff. New York: Vintage.
- Lin Lougheed, 1976. *Educational Measurement third Editor*. New York: American communal on, Educational. Acemillan
- Pappas, George, Oson David, 1970. *Perspectives' Children Language and Language Teaching Arts*, February 227-229
- Sudjana, Nana.2010. *Penilaian Hasil Proses Belajar Mengajar*.Bandung; Rosda Karya.

- Rivers, Tarigan, 1968. *Teaching Foreign Language Skill*. Chicago University Press.
- Widdowso, H.G, 1990. *Teaching Language As Communication*, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Wiryacitra, 1982. *Ascientific Reading Program Teaching English Forum*, 3 Volume.
- Zinzit Magart, 1989. *The Reading Proses, The Teacher And The Learner*, U.S.A.